

EXTERNAL PRESSURE TESTING OF A LARGE-SCALE COMPOSITE PIPE

Guillermo Ramirez¹ and Michael D. Engelhardt²

¹ *Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of Kansas
2006 Learned Hall, Lawrence, Kansas, 66045-2234, USA*

² *Department of Civil Engineering, Offshore Technology Research Center
The University of Texas at Austin, Ferguson Structural Engineering Laboratory,
10100 Burnet Road, Austin, Texas, 78758, USA*

SUMMARY: An external pressure test was conducted on a full-scale diameter prototype composite offshore drilling riser. The test specimen was a carbon fiber – epoxy filament wound tube, approximately 55.9 cm (22 in) outside diameter and 3.05 cm (1.2 in) wall thickness. The tube was subjected to external water pressure up to collapse. The purpose of the test was to confirm the external pressure capacity of the tube, and to provide a basis for verification and calibration of analytical estimates of the collapse pressure for composites. The specimen was instrumented with strain gages on both the outside and inside walls of the tube, and was monitored with a digital acoustic emission system. This paper will describe the test specimen, and will summarize key results of the test.

KEYWORDS: buckling, carbon fiber, composite structures, offshore applications, acoustic emission, nondestructive evaluation

INTRODUCTION

The move towards exploration and development of petroleum reserves at ever increasing water depth has motivated the development of drilling and production systems that are more efficient than the ones currently in place. This has resulted in the proposed use of alternative materials like advanced fiber reinforced composites. The weight savings offered by these materials is a potentially significant economic advantage in floating deep water offshore platforms, and advanced composites are currently under consideration for a number of applications in the platforms, including drilling and production risers. At present, risers are typically constructed of steel. However, as water depths exceed several thousand feet, the large weight of the riser becomes increasingly difficult and costly to accommodate, thereby motivating interest in lighter weight materials [1]. However, before lightweight advanced composites can be applied with confidence for offshore oil production, comprehensive research and testing is needed to develop and verify design criteria.

The cost and time required in the initial development of systems constructed using composite materials makes testing of full size components unique and difficult. Therefore, the majority of the material characterization data comes from tests performed in scaled down specimens whose dimensions are much smaller than the actual components. Nonetheless, a limited number of large-scale tests are valuable as an aid in extrapolating data from small-scale tests, for verifying analytical models and to help identify unanticipated scale effects.

This paper presents the results of an external pressure test on a carbon fiber composite tube. The specimen represented the main body of a proposed carbon fiber drilling riser, at full scale in diameter and wall thickness. The specimen was tested under external water pressure up to collapse. The test was intended to verify the capability of the specimen to sustain the design external pressure, to establish the actual collapse pressure, and to generate data for verification of analytical collapse pressure predictions. As an added variable, a full length, complete radial delamination was present at mid-thickness at the tube wall. A description of the specimen properties as well as the testing program and results are presented in this paper. In addition, preliminary comparisons to simplified collapse predictions for steel and composite materials are made.

SPECIMEN PREPARATION

The specimen was fabricated using aerospace-grade carbon fiber and an epoxy resin. The specimen used in this program was 4.57 m (15 ft) in length, had an outside diameter of 56.39 cm (22.2 in) and a wall thickness of 3.05 cm (1.2 in). Geometric tolerances met or exceeded API requirements for steel components of the same geometry. The specimen represents the main body of a proposed carbon fiber drilling riser but did not include end connectors. Due to problems encountered during filament winding of the tube, a delamination occurred at approximately mid-thickness of the tube wall.

Before testing, measurements were made of the specimen to verify dimensions and tolerances and characterize initial geometric imperfections. In addition, an ultrasonic test was performed to define the extent of the delamination present in the specimen. The measurements indicated that the delamination extended the entire perimeter and length of the tube.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

The specimen was subjected to external water pressure inside a large chamber. The test was intended to subject the composite tube to a state of pure external pressure, without axial compression stresses resulting from pressure on the end caps of the specimen. In addition, the assembly allowed for the free axial deformation of the tube induced by the Poisson effect resulting from the hoop stresses. The final configuration of the test specimen is presented in the Figure 1.

The seal system was required to allow for the axial movement of the composite tube while keeping the interior of the specimen dry. In addition, since the complete assembly was to be enclosed in the pressure chamber, it was necessary to account for the axial force resulting from the pressure acting at the ends of the specimen. A 35.56 cm (14 in) diameter steel pipe was used as interior filler to resist the axial thrust caused by water pressure acting on the end caps. Figure 2 shows the final configuration of the seal system.

Instrumentation included strain gages located at selected locations on the inner and outer surfaces of the tube. In addition, the use of acoustic emission (AE) monitoring was included during the test for indications of onset of significant damage mechanisms (matrix cracking, delaminations, fiber breakage, etc) occurring at various pressure levels. Figure 3 shows the locations for the strain rosettes and the location for the AE sensors.

TEST RESULTS

During testing, external pressure was increased in steps, with a number of partial unloading and reloading cycles (Figure 4), up to final collapse of the tube. The pressurization sequence was chosen to facilitate acquisition of meaningful acoustic emissions data, and was based on recommendations provided in Ref. 2. Loading was increased until collapse, which occurred at 21.72 MPa (3150 psi).

As a result of seal failures, the specimen was loaded in three separate occasions. The first loading was to 1,723 kPa (250 psi), with the second reaching 4,825.8 kPa (700 psi) and followed by a third and final loading to failure. Comparing the measured strains for all three tests it was apparent that no permanent deformation was incurred during the first two loadings. The behavior of the strain gages was almost identical when compared at the same pressure levels in all tests. Acoustic emission data is difficult to compare since the flow noise generated by the leaking seals obscured the records from the first two tests.

The measured strains for the final test are presented in the Figure 5. For convenience, the scale of the horizontal axis is reversed, negative strains (red) are in the right side, positive (black in the left). The measured axial strains at mid-length of the pipe showed somewhat unexpected behavior. At low pressures, the axial strain increased with increasing pressure as expected. However, at higher pressures, the axial strains at mid-length change sign, and in general, show somewhat erratic behavior.

Both external axial gages at mid-length of the pipe showed similar trends, suggesting that the observed behavior was not the result of a defective gage. Note that the axial gages at the quarter length of the tube did not show this anomalous behavior. These gages showed

increasing axial strain at all pressure levels. The unusual trends of the middle gages were the subject of additional studies with the use of finite element modeling techniques.

A finite element model using the ANSYS™ code was created to track and compare the recorded behavior of the strain gages. The model consisted of a symmetrical section of the tube modeled with two separate conditions. One of the models (Figure 6) included the delamination at the same location as the one in the full-scale specimen. The second or solid model was created with the same material properties as the delamination model, but without the delamination. The first model was calibrated with the use of the recorded strain data and AE information obtained during the test. The calibration consisted of modifying the material properties at the ply level, resulting in a close match to the strains measured at the low-pressure ranges during the tests. The results from this calibration process are shown in Figure 7. No other forms of calibration were utilized in the model. Contact elements were used at the interface of the delamination. The effect of friction was also

Material Properties

considered during the analysis phase. Buckling loads were obtained using a large deformation nonlinear analysis in both models.

As it can be seen in the figure, the difference between the expressions for the modulus E is the one more affected by the calibration. The mismatch seems to be more forgiving for the values of G and ν than for E. The final values used in the analysis were:

$$\xi = 0.57 \text{ for } E \quad (1)$$

$$\xi = 1 + 65V_f^{10} \text{ for } G \text{ and } \nu \quad (2)$$

All the properties resulting from this calibration are good only for the particular test presented and cannot be extrapolated beyond it. This limits their usefulness greatly and may even make some of the observations made invalid. Lack of supporting tests to specimens with non flawed condition or cross-section is a great obstacle. Nevertheless the data presented here provided with some interesting trends that may be used to support observations developed in other programs with more extensive testing component. Large scale testing is scarce and material properties obtained from these tests are extremely valuable in the developing of a more complete understanding of full-scale composite material elements and components.

The use of the AE data was critical in the determination of the approach used during the creation and calibration of the FE model. A cursory evaluation of the AE data obtained during the final test showed that the main mechanisms of damage were likely those associated with matrix cracking and delamination. No emission typically associated with fiber breakage was recorded until the collapse pressure was reached. Since the reinforcing fibers are responsible

for the stiffness it was therefore assumed that, the stiffness of the tube remained the same for most of the loading profile. Acoustic emission data recorded during the early stages of the test support the possibility that movement between the layers was taking place

Looking at the strain plot from the FEA results in Figure 10, it can be seen that the model predicted contact of the separate rings at about this same pressure. In addition, the recorded strains show a change in the stiffness of the specimen at the same level. The prediction of the external pressure at contact obtained from the model is dependent on the assumed size of the initial gap. The calibrated gap used was 12.7 mm (0.005 in) between the inner and outer rings. It should be noted that a range of gaps were studied ranging from 25.4 to 2.54 mm (0.01 to 0.001 in). Buckling loads obtained from each of the analysis did not deviate by more than 5%. Therefore, the influence of the gap assumed appears critical only to the predicted external pressure and strains levels at contact.

Figure 11 shows the hoop strains measured at the exterior and interior surfaces at mid-length of the riser. The curves initially deviate from each other, showing higher strains on the exterior as compared to the interior. At higher pressures, the two curves appear to converge to approximately the same hoop strain. The initial divergence of these curves, followed by their convergence, is also predicted with the FE model. This deviation is the result of lack of full contact between the two rings. As the pressure was increased, the outside ring closed onto the inner ring, resulting in the hoop deformation at this ring.

Collapse pressure was reached at 21.72 MPa (3150 psi) when the specimen failed in a sudden manner. Figure 12 shows the calculated collapse pressure or 20.27 MPa (2.94 ksi) with the FE model. Since calibration of the material properties was performed only with the low pressure records and no subsequent reduction was made to these properties, it can be inferred that the failure was one of essentially elastic instability. The majority of the breaking fibers recorded by the AE took place at the time of collapse when deformations reached levels larger than the strain capacity of the fibers. The AE records suggests some limited amount of fiber breakage was occurring at the higher-pressure levels.

COMPARISON WITH SIMPLIFIED PREDICTION MODELS

Table 1 presents a comparison of the 21.72 MPa (3150 psi) measured collapse pressure with the collapse pressure predicted by simplified equations used in several design codes for tubular members. These codes cover both steel (API-LRFD RP2A) and composite members (British Standard, French Code, ASME RTP, ASME Section X). The table shows that most of the simplified criteria predicted a value that was very close to the measured collapse pressure. In the calculation of the pressure, all safety factors were reduced to 1.0.

Table 1 Simplified prediction models

Predictions of Ultimate Collapse Pressure				
Specification	Measured Collapse Pressure = 21.72 MPa			
	Predicted Value with $E_{estimated}$ (A)	Predicted Value with $E_{measured}$ (B)	(A) Predicted / Measured	(B) Predicted / Measured
API-LRFD RP2A (3)	21.65 MPa	20.48 MPa	0.99	0.94
British Standard (4)	23.23 MPa	22.00 MPa	1.07	1.01
French Code (5)	23.23 MPa	22.00 MPa	1.07	1.01
ASME RTP Code (6)	16.00 MPa	15.17 MPa	0.74	0.70
ASME Section X (7)	12.55 MPa	11.86 MPa	0.58	0.55

Although some of the criteria appear to predict an acceptable value, the code predictions of collapse strength must be viewed with caution. These formulas are adjusted to take into account initial imperfections in the geometry of the pipe or vessel in question and typically, do not include effects of flaws or differences in the material manufacture or properties. These factors are taken into account in the material strength used in the calculations. These simple comparisons seem to suggest that the delamination in the specimen did not have a significant influence in the collapse pressure contrary to the predictions of the FE analysis. Interestingly, the prediction model that performed the best, in terms of predicting the closest value to the measured capacity was API(3) which is intended for steel tubulars. Further testing and analysis is necessary before a definite conclusion can be reached on the accuracy and applicability of simplified equations for collapse pressure prediction of composite tubulars.

SUMMARY

A full-scale carbon fiber composite tube was tested under external pressure up to collapse. Initial observations of strain gage and acoustic emission data show some unexpected trends that may be related to the presence of a delamination in the tube wall. Finite element analyses help explain many of the trends seen in the strain gages and AE sensors data. Predictions made using FE models with and without a delamination suggest a significant reduction in collapse pressure occurred as a result of the existing delamination. Nonetheless, simplified analytical predictions of collapse pressure agree reasonably well with the measured value.

Further detail analyses are underway to better understand the measured response of the test specimen and further evaluate analytical methods for predicting collapse of composite tubes.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge financial support for this project provided by the NIST Advanced Technology Program and by the Offshore Technology Research Center. The test specimen provided by Northrop-Grumman Marine Systems, and the assistance of Bill Anderson and Craig Mickelson of Northrop-Grumman is appreciated. In addition, the authors would like to express their gratitude to Dr. Timothy Fowler and Yajai of the University of Texas at Austin for their assistance in the monitoring of Acoustic Emission during the tests. The authors also gratefully acknowledge the assistance provided by H.O. Mohr Research & Engineering Company in Houston in conducting this test

REFERENCES

1. E.D Valenzuela, and W.F Anderson et all, 1993. Comparative Performance of a Composite Drilling Riser in Deep Water. OTC 7263, Offshore Technology Conference.
2. SPI Composites Institute, Recommended Practice for Acoustic Emission Testing of Fiberglass Reinforced Plastic Resin (RP) Tanks/Vessels.
3. API RP 2A-LRFD “Planing, Designing and Constructing Fixed Offshore Platforms”, Load Resistance Factor Design, 1993, Section D, Cylindrical Member Design, pg.49-54
4. British Standard for Design and Construction of Vessels and Tanks in Reinforced Plastics, BS4994-1987.
5. Code de Construction des Appareils Chaudronnes en Plastique Arme, Commission Chaudronnerie, Genie Chimique du Syndicat General de L’Industrie du Plastique Arme, France, December 1976.
6. American Society of Mechanical Engineers, Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code, Section 10, New York, 1989.
7. Reinforced Thermoset Plastic Corrosion Resistant Equipment. The American Society of Mechanical Engineers, ASME-ANSI-RTP-1989.
8. S.V. Hoa, Analysis for Design of Fiber Reinforced Plastic Vessels and Pipings.
9. Jones, R.M., *Mechanics of Composite Materials*, International Student Edition, MacGraw-Hill Kogakusha Ltd, Tokyo, 1975